

Supplementary information

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S1 Homophilic and heterophilic graph

In homophilic graphs, nodes with similar features or identical labels are assumed to form densely connected clusters, a pattern frequently observed in social and citation networks. As illustrated in Fig.S1, papers within a specific domain preferentially cite references from the same field rather than disparate disciplines. Based on this prior, GNNs benefit from the classic message passing (MP) strategy to exchange information among proximal neighbors, and with iterative propagation expanding the receptive field as layer depth increases.

Instead, the interaction of cancer genes exhibits heterophily. Their scarcity leads them to contradict the concept of homophily graphs. This concept was first observed in fraud networks, where malicious actors often interact with normal users to conceal illegal activities. This concept was originally observed in fraud networks, where malicious actors often interact with normal users to obscure illegal activities.

Fig. S1 Homophilic citation network (left) and heterophilic biomolecule network (right).

S2 GNN and standard MP limitation

As shown in Fig.S2, in cancer gene networks, traditional message-passing GNNs have several major bottlenecks:

(1) Most methods limit interactions to immediate neighbors, so that more non-cancer genes (heterophilic nodes) are captured; (2) Even though a few methods hope to expand to the global structure to capture cancer genes (homophilic nodes), fixing the distance and the same scale of receptive field for all nodes will result in heterophilic information that is weakly or even oppositely correlated with the central cancer genes being mixed into the representation; (3) With the iteration of MP, features from different hops are superimposed on each other (K hop $\rightarrow K - 1$ hop $\rightarrow \dots \rightarrow 1$ hop), which easily causes information to dilute and tend to be confused; (4) For the central node, neighbors with direct and indirect dual identities are repeatedly calculated. For example, node 1 undergoes two aggregations in the first and second layers of the GNN. This both increases computational overhead and exacerbates noise accumulation, making it difficult for the model to capture the unique identity of each gene.

These findings suggest that graph representation learning methods for cancer gene identification must seek breakthroughs in structural diversity rather than simply stacking layers.

Fig. S2 A toy example used to help illustrate the bottlenecks faced by traditional graph representation learning methods.

S3 Explanation of three different architectures

Comprehensive performance and ablation studies have demonstrated the advantages of CGMap. However, to more intuitively explain the rationality of its architecture, we progressively present the differences between three architectures, including traditional GNN, streamlined GNN, and width-guided streamlined GNN. As shown in Fig.S3, the left half uses a simplified toy example to illustrate the information flow pipelines of the three architectures. The right side is their formal definitions.

- Traditional GNN: Node features are alternately executed by coupled propagation and transformation modules (standard message passing). Neighbor representations are aggregated to the central node in a stacked layer-by-layer manner.
- Streamlined GNN (i.e., CGMap without OPP): The transformation is separated from the propagation while retaining the core propagation method in standard MP.
- Width-guided streamlined GNN (CGMap): Retains the simplified GNN backbone and uses the shortest path to guide the selection of different-order neighbor sets. At the same time, the propagation process avoids layer stacking and instead uses parallel neighborhood sets to expand the GNN.

We can observe that if the propagation pattern in the streamlined GNN still uses layer-wise stacking, representation convergence cannot be avoided. The blue heatmap shows a gradual diffusion of gray tones as propagation increases. Width-guided propagation achieves an effect similar to dilated convolutions. Its heatmap exhibits distinct sparse and dense patterns at each scale. As propagation depth increases, the heatmaps show clearer layering, as nodes with longer shortest paths are less frequent. This also explains why convergence has the least impact in CGMap.

Fig. S3 Explanation of the differences between the three architectures.

S4 Detailed statistics and heterophilic metric of datasets

Table S1 Benchmark dataset detailed statistics.

Network	Nodes	Edges	Positive	Negative	H.R.*	Average Degree	Edge density
PPI	11395	285,843	716	1026	0.899	50.17	0.0088
PathNet	7695	92,710	598	701	0.876	24.10	0.0063
GGNet	11183	621,988	708	1101	0.943	111.24	0.0199

*Heterophily Ratio. H.R closer to 1 means the network is more heterophilic and vice versa is more homophilic.

Table S1 provides detailed statistics on the dataset used in this study, including the number of nodes, edges, positive/negative samples, and some common network metrics. The number of known cancer genes is much smaller than the total number of genes, which is considered an imbalanced scenario classification task.

In addition, we designed a heterophily ratio metric H.R to quantify the connection patterns between cancer genes and non-cancer genes in the network. The metric calculates the proportion of edges connected to cancer genes and non-cancer genes among the edges associated with cancer genes, formalized as follows:

$$\text{H.R} = \frac{|\{(u, v) \in \mathcal{E} \mid \ell_u \neq \ell_v \wedge (\ell_u = 1 \vee \ell_v = 1)\}|}{|\{(u, v) \in \mathcal{E} \mid \ell_u = 1 \vee \ell_v = 1\}|} \quad (1)$$

where \mathcal{E} represents the edge set and ℓ indicates the gene node label. This indicator reflects the tendency of cancer gene partners to interact in the network. It can be found that in this sparse cancer gene scenario, the network implies natural heterophily. Cancer genes are more likely to be connected to other genes, and H.R increases with the complexity of network connections.

S5 CGMap against oversmoothing

Fig. S4 Performance changes of 1-10-layer CGMap on PathNet (top) and GGNet (bottom) networks.

S6 Unify the weights of each layer

GPR weights dynamically adjust the influence of each layer, enabling the model to prioritize layers with greater information content. To investigate this effect, we modified the GPR weights to a uniform weight across all layers. Specifically, we set the weights in GGNet, PathNet, and PPI to $1/K$, where K is the number of layers.

The results are shown in Fig.S5, and we have the following observations: (1) Overall, CGMap with GPR weights demonstrated higher performance, with consistent results across layers. In contrast, variants with uniform weights saw a performance decline of up to 2.84%; (2) Even when the weights are changed to the same for each layer, the performance of the variants still increases with the number of layers. This once again confirms our conclusion that long-range dependencies are beneficial for gene prediction. (3) Although PPI deviates slightly from the conclusion due to the small-world principle, the advantage of GPR weights is still obvious.

Fig. S5 Performance differences between CGMap and changing GPR weights to the same value on three networks.

S7 Enrichment result of regulatory pathways tracked by CGMap

Fig. S6 Enrichment of these pathways with $1 \leq L \leq 2$ in KEGG, REACTOME, and DisGeNET, confirming CGMap's ability to track actual biological processes.

S8 Enhanced fidelity

Fig. S7 The t-SNE visualization results verified the consistency of gene embeddings on the other two networks with the original network embeddings.

S9 Enhanced prediction stability under data skew constraints

Fig. S8 Performance of CGMap on PathNet (top) and GGNet (bottom) networks compared to representative baselines under different proportional data skew constraints.

S10 Enhanced prediction robustness under structural disturbance constraints

Fig. S9 Performance of CGMap on PathNet (top) and GGNet (bottom) networks compared to representative baselines under different proportional data skew constraints.

S11 Gene intersection list

Table S2 A set of high-confidence candidate cancer genes from CGMap, with the bold ones being the novel candidates genes.

PIK3CA	TTN	TP53	MUC16	PTEN
CTNNB1	KMT2D	APC	KRAS	KMT2C
RYR2	FAT4	EP300	ATM	NOTCH1
PIK3R1	FAT1	CREBBP	CDH1	APOB
DMD	PCLO	SPTA1	OBSCN	LRP2
HRAS	BRAF	SMAD4	FBXW7	NCOR1
AKT1	KMT2A	RYR3	MAP3K1	ZFHX3
MUC4	VHL	ANK3	NRAS	CASP8
ACTB	SPOP	NEB	RYR1	SPTAN1
CHD4	KDM6A	PCDH15	AKAP9	DNAH9
GATA3	FN1	COL11A1	CUBN	RB1
ANK2	PRKDC	PLEC	HSPG2	NF1
RIMS2	ERBB2	COL6A3	VCAN	TGFBR2
MTOR	JAK1	SMARCA4	NOTCH2	MET

Fig. S11 The Kaplan-Meier curve obtained using the Gepia2 database shows the relationship between the expression level of the significant candidates genes in TCGA cancer and the survival prognosis (95% confidence interval is indicated by a dotted line). The hazard ratio (HR) was calculated based on the Cox proportional hazard model, with the high expression group as the intervention group [HR (high)].

Fig. S12 Immune infiltration analysis of TTN, PCLO, LRP2, RYR2 and RYR3 genes. For TTN gene, we prioritized CD8+T and NK cells; PCLO prioritized CD8+T, B, Tregs cells; LRP2 prioritized the functional status of macrophages, Tregs and DCs cells; RYR2 and RYR3 focused on the immunosuppressive functional status of CD8+T, Tregs and MDSCs.

Fig. S13 Single-cell functional enrichment of remaining novel candidates.

S13 Detailed protocol for cancer cell line validation

Materials. The materials and reagents employed in this study include: primary antibodies against E-Cadherin (#3195), N-Cadherin (#13116), Vimentin (#5741), Vinculin (#4650) and beta-Tubulin (#2146) were purchased from Cell Signaling Technology (Danvers, MA, USA). Additional primary antibodies against Fibronectin (FN1) (ab32419) and Titin (TTN) (ab284860) were acquired from Abcam (Cambridge, MA, USA), Ki67/MKI67 (#M00254-9) antibody was obtained from Bosterbio (Wuhan, China). Fluorescent secondary antibody (#A32723), DAPI (#D1306), Lipofectamine RNAiMAX (#13778075), RIPA buffer (#89900) and BCA Protein Assay Kit (#23225) were obtained from Thermo Fisher Scientific (Waltham, MA, USA). The Cell Counting Kit-8 (CCK-8) (#HY-K0301) and Crystal Violet (#HY-B0324A) were purchased from MedChemExpress (New Jersey, USA).

Cell Culture. Human LUAD cell line A549 and TNBC cell line MDA-MB-231 were obtained from the Chinese Academy of Sciences cell bank (Shanghai, China). Human GBM cell line U251 was kindly provided by Dr. Bin Liao (The Second Affiliated Hospital of Nanchang University). A549 cell line was cultured in RPMI-1640 medium, MDA-MB-231 and U251 cell lines were cultured in DMEM medium, respectively, supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS), penicillin (50 µg/ml), and streptomycin (50 µg/ml). Cells were maintained at 37°C in a 5% CO₂ incubator. The cell lines were authenticated by STR profiling and tested routinely before use to avoid mycoplasma contamination.

FN1 and TTN knockdown. To knockdown FN1 and TTN, three siRNAs targeting each of their mRNA were designed. All siRNAs were purchased from OBiO Technology (Shanghai, China) and validated by sequencing. Transfection was done using Lipofectamine RNAiMAX as per the manufacturer's instructions.

Western blotting (WB). Total cellular protein was extracted using RIPA lysis buffer supplemented with protease inhibitors, and protein concentration was determined via the BCA assay. 30-50 µg of protein per well were loaded into SDS-PAGE gels (7.5% or 10%) for separation, followed by wet transfer onto 0.45 µm PVDF membranes. The membranes were blocked with 5% skim milk at room temperature for 1 hour, then incubated with primary antibodies (dilution 1:1000) overnight at 4°C. Subsequently, the membranes were incubated with appropriate HRP-conjugated secondary antibodies (dilution 1:10000) at room temperature for 1 hour. Detection was performed using chemiluminescent substrate, and images were captured using a chemiluminescence imaging system.

CCK-8 assay. Cells transfected during the logarithmic growth phase were seeded into 96-well plates at a density of 1000 cells per well, with six replicate wells per group. Following cell attachment, measurements were performed at 0, 24, 48, and 72 hours: 10 µL of CCK-8 reagent was directly added to each well, which was then incubated in the dark at 37°C for 2 hours. Subsequently, the absorbance (OD value) of each well was measured at a wavelength of 450 nm using a microplate reader.

Cell Scratch Assay. Cells were seeded into 6-well plates at a density of 5×10^5 cells per well and cultured until confluency was achieved overnight. A 200 μ L sterile pipette tip was used to create a linear scratch along the cell monolayer, guided by a ruler. The cells and debris were gently washed twice with PBS to remove detached fragments, and the medium was replaced with Opti-MEM supplemented with 0.5% FBS for maintenance. The plates were then incubated in a cell culture incubator. Images were captured at 0, 12, 24, and 48 hours post-scratch using a $4\times$ objective lens.

Transwell Cell Invasion Assay. The experiment utilized Transwell chambers with an 8.0 μ m pore size. Initially, Matrigel matrix gel (thawed overnight at 4°C) was diluted with pre-cooled serum-free culture medium at a ratio of 1:8. A 50 μ L aliquot of the diluted Matrigel was evenly applied to the upper surface of the polycarbonate membrane within the chamber. The chamber was then incubated at 37°C for 2 hours to allow for basement membrane formation, followed by hydration with 200 μ L of serum-free culture medium for 30 minutes. Cells subjected to serum starvation for 12 hours were subsequently digested and resuspended, with 5×10^4 cells seeded onto the Matrigel-coated upper chamber. The lower chamber was filled with 600 μ L of complete culture medium containing 10% FBS as a chemoattractant. Cells were allowed to invade at 37°C in a 5% CO_2 atmosphere for 24 hours. After incubation, non-invaded cells on the upper chamber were removed with a cotton swab. The cells that had migrated to the underside of the membrane were fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde, washed with PBS, and stained with 0.1% crystal violet. Photographs were taken under a microscope for analysis.

Immunofluorescence (IF). Cells were seeded onto sterile coverslips placed in 24-well plates and cultured until reaching the appropriate confluence, followed by transfection. The cells were fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde at room temperature for 15 minutes, permeabilized with 0.5% Triton X-100 for 20 minutes, and subsequently blocked with 5% bovine serum albumin (BSA) at room temperature for 1 hour. The cells were then incubated overnight at 4°C with an anti-Ki67 primary antibody (diluted 1:200). After washing with PBS, the samples were incubated with an Alexa Fluor 488-conjugated secondary antibody (diluted 1:500) at room temperature in the dark for 1 hour. Finally, the coverslips were mounted with a DAPI-containing mounting medium, and images were captured using a fluorescence confocal microscope for observation.

Statistical analysis. Experimental data were obtained from three independent replicates and presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Statistical analyses were performed using GraphPad Prism version 10.0. Unpaired t-tests were applied to analyze data, with significance levels indicated as follows: ns, no significance, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, and *** $p < 0.001$.

Fig. S14 Figure S12. Western blot analysis demonstrated the expression levels of FN1 (A) and TTN (B) in three cancer cell lines. It illustrated knockdown of FN1 or TTN achieved via RNA interference. NC, negative control. Vinculin was used as a loading control.